

BROADBAND OPERATION OF A TWO-STAGE TAPERED GYRO-TWT AMPLIFIER

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ABSTRACT

A two-stage Ka-band gyro-TWT amplifier experiment operating in the TE₁₀ rectangular tapered waveguide mode at the fundamental cyclotron frequency is underway at the Naval Research Laboratory. The objective of this program is to demonstrate the stable wideband operation of a low voltage tapered gyro-TWT having high gain and good gain uniformity. Initial experiments operating at 33kV and 1.5A have demonstrated a linear gain of 30dB, saturated gain of 26dB over an 8% 3dB-bandwidth, and maximum efficiency of 15%. The operation will be compared with theory.

INTRODUCTION

A continuing need exists for broadband high power sources of millimeter wave radiation. Fast wave amplifiers based on the electron cyclotron maser instability, such as the gyro-TWT, have the potential to provide high powers at high frequencies. Earlier gyro-TWT research^{1,2,3} has demonstrated that a bandwidth of 10% could be realized in a uniform circuit. Recently research at the National Tsing Hua University showed a saturated gain of 20dB and 23% efficiency over 10% bandwidth at 90kV and 1.5A by driver-suppressed oscillation in a single stage Ka-band circuit with TE₁₁ operating mode,¹ and 35dB saturated gain and 16% efficiency over 7.5% bandwidth with the same beam in a two-stage severed Ka-band circuit.² Varian Associates reported 20dB saturated gain and 26% efficiency over 7.25% bandwidth at 65kV and 7A in a single stage C-band circuit with TE₁₁ operating mode.³ Due to well-known spurious oscillations at the absolute instability and multi-path reflection, the previous experiments employed a relatively high voltage and low beam velocity ratio, $\alpha = vt/vz \sim 1$. The approach taken at NRL, however, for wideband operation is to employ a tapered rectangular waveguide and tapered magnetic field operating at low beam voltage (33kV). Previously,⁴ a bandwidth of more than 30% has been achieved in a single stage tapered Ka-band gyro-TWT at NRL. The device employed a single port reflection-type circuit operating in the rectangular TE₁₀ waveguide mode at a beam voltage of 33 kV and 1.5 A. Stable operation was obtained by reducing

the beam α to around 0.6 and by carefully tapering the waveguide cutoff frequency and external magnetic field over the interaction region. As expected for a single port reflection-type amplifier, the high gain operation of the tube was strongly influenced by multi-pass interference effects. The maximum stable small signal gain of the tube was limited by the rf window match to around 25 dB. Tube operation in excess of 20 dB, however, resulted in excessive gain fluctuations across the amplification band. The tube performance, therefore, was optimized at a linear gain of around 20 dB. In this regime, narrowband large signal measurements were performed demonstrating a peak output power of 5 kW (9% efficiency) with a saturated gain of 17 dB. The use of a tapered interaction circuit has both advantages and disadvantages regarding amplifier stability. The use of an inhomogeneous circuit effectively increases the beam current threshold for oscillation over the uniform circuit value. However, since the tapered configuration does not readily admit the inclusion of circuit loss in the output stage, the rf performance of the tapered amplifier depends sensitively on the output circuit match. Recently, a two-stage tapered gyro-TWT has been designed and constructed. The tube is designed to provide a reduced gain per stage for enhanced stability and gain flatness. Nonlinear device calculations⁵ indicate an efficiency of 30% (10kW) with a 15% bandwidth for a 33 kV, 1.2 A beam with α of 0.9 (at the lower end of the band) and a 2% spread in axial velocity. The simulations show that the gain-bandwidth response is very sensitive to the beam velocity spread.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup of the two stage tapered gyro-TWT is shown in Figure 1. A 1.5 A, 33 kV annular electron beam, produced from a double anode MIG, is adiabatically compressed to the beam velocity ratio α of 0.8 at the entrance of the tapered waveguide circuit. The two-stage tapered circuit consists of three sections: a linearly down-tapered rectangular waveguide (input section), a 1" long waveguide cutoff sever section ($f_{co} = 39.4$ GHz), and a linearly up-tapered rectangular waveguide (output section). The rf drive chain consists of a frequency synthesizer and a 50 W

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TWT. The rf is injected into the input section through a broadband sidewall directional coupler. The measurements show a coupling value of better than -1 dB and a return loss < -25 dB over full Ka-band (26.5 - 40 GHz); in good agreement with the 3-D electromagnetic code HFSS.⁶ (Dots indicate HFSS results in Figure 2.) The amplified rf signal in the input section is reflected at waveguide cutoff and coupled back to a matched load through the input directional coupler. The amplified rf power in the output section is extracted directly through a 2" long linear transition to Ka-band waveguide. The width of the circuit varies from 0.24" ($f_{co} = 24.6$ GHz) to 0.15" ($f_{co} = 39.4$ GHz) along an 8" length in the input section and from 0.15" to 0.24" along a 12" length in the output section. The circuit height throughout its axial extent remains constant at 0.14". The total length of the two stage circuit (21") is the same as in the previous single-stage gyro-TWT experiment. The input and output tapering lengths have been designed to provide around 30 dB of total gain. Thin (<1mil) mica sheets are used as the rf vacuum windows and as DC breaks for monitoring the circuit and collector current. Cold test measurements on the rf windows show a return loss of -23 dB, thereby satisfying the amplifier stability condition regarding reflection instability (roundtrip gain less than unity) in both the input and output stages. The magnetic field profile is obtained by using a computer controlled, 14-coil superconducting magnet system. The individual coil currents required are obtained from a magnetic field synthesis code. To satisfy the beam quality requirement, three water-cooled magnet trim coils are energized in the gun region to insure a flat field at the cathode. The measured magnetic field profile is seen to be in good agreement with the calculated profile, as shown in Fig. 3. The field varies from 9.4 kG at the entrance of circuit to 14.3 kG at the cutoff section for the following measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 4 shows the saturation of the two-stage tapered gyro-TWT using a 50W TWT driving amplifier. The TWT generates about 50W from 32 GHz to 37 GHz. Electronic efficiency of 15% has been measured at 33kV and 1.5A with operating frequency of 36 GHz, as shown in Fig. 4. The gain is seen to have improved with the two-stage circuit, as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, over the value for the single stage tapered circuit. Linear gain has improved from 23dB to 30dB and saturated gain increased from 17dB to 26dB. The gain fluctuation of ± 4 dB at the linear gain of 23dB observed previously with the single stage tapered gyro-TWT is observed to decrease significantly to about ± 1 dB at 30dB gain for the two-stage tapered gyro-TWT. The gain fluctuation is a sensitive function of the

reflection coefficients of the circuit and the gain of the amplifier. In general, the larger the per-stage gain of the device, the larger the fluctuation amplitude in the output signal. In Fig. 5 (Fig. 6), the first and second stage gain is around 9dB(14dB) and 16dB(14dB), respectively. As expected, the reduced gain per stage of the two-stage configuration is found to significantly improve the gain flatness across the band over a single stage high gain design.

DISCUSSION

At the time of this publication, the gun trim coils were not yet operational, thereby limiting device optimization regarding bandwidth and efficiency. Optimization of amplifier performance, however, is currently in progress. Since the gain per stage is reduced (14dB rather than 25dB) in the two-stage device, stable amplifier operation is possible at higher electron beam α than for the single stage device and higher device efficiency can be expected. The reflective instability which limits the performance of the single stage tapered gyro-TWT is now not expected to be a dominant issue. Overall, the two-stage gyro-TWT is expected to produce a two-stage gain of ~ 30 dB, an electronic efficiency of 20 - 30%, and an instantaneous bandwidth > 15% for α 's between 0.6 - 0.8 and $\Delta v_z/v_z = 2\%$. Key issues to be confronted in optimizing the efficiency and bandwidth of the two-stage tapered gyro-TWT are electron beam quality and accurate magnetic field profiling.

CONCLUSION

A high gain broadband low voltage two-stage tapered gyro-TWT has been designed and tested. Preliminary experiments have demonstrated a linear gain of 30dB, saturated gain of 26dB over 8% 3dB-bandwidth, and maximum efficiency of 15% operating at 33kV and 1.5A. The experimental investigation of the optimum operation of the two-stage tapered gyro-TWT is underway and comparison with theory will be presented.

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Figure 1. Experimental setup of two-stage tapered gyro-TWT

Figure 2. Coupling value measurement of the input coupler (Dots indicate HFSS-results).

Figure 3. Measurement of magnetic field profile

Figure 4. Saturated efficiency measurement

Figure 5. Saturated gain measurement

Figure 6. Linear gain measurement